

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
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A MENTOR: A FRAMEWORK FOR EMPOWERING THE AMBULATORY CARE
CLINICIAN IN PATIENT SATISFACTION

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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May 2014

ABSTRACT

In the ambulatory healthcare care setting, patient satisfaction has been shown to impact perceived quality of care and patient outcomes. A review of literature demonstrates that while patient satisfaction measures are valuable, they tend to lack specificity. Patient concerns, however, provide insight into the particulars of the patient experience and create an opportunity for improvement. A MENTOR serves as the framework for this quality improvement project that aims to empower healthcare providers to anticipate and address expectations, manage the patient as a customer, establish rapport, negotiate and partner, treat the clinical and customer diagnoses, offer clarification, and recognize concerns and reinforce realistic expectations and solutions. In doing so, patient concerns can be mitigated before they occur through a process of prevention. Training was accomplished through a series of sequential face to face in-services, each focused on best practices around the management of billing, clinical, and facility related topics that make up the total patient experience. Both nurse practitioners and licensed vocational nurses were exposed to the A MENTOR training which was carried out over four sessions. A rise in self-reported confidence levels occurred following the completion of the series. Ultimately, the A MENTOR framework serves to support the enhancement of the health care provider's customer service skills in the ambulatory care setting in order to enhance the patient-provider relationship. At the organizational level, A MENTOR is applicable, teaching all staff how to optimize the patient's perception of their care which drives patient loyalty and positive outcomes.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project would not be possible without the invaluable wisdom and support of Dr. Paula Vuckovich. Thank you, Dr. Vuckovich, for your guidance, and for leading me down the path of this incredible academic journey as my project chair. I would also like to thank Dr. Penny Weismuller for her dedication to this project and to the entire doctoral process. To my personal and professional colleague, Marlaine Skaggs, FNP, your mentorship was critical to the realization of my vision for this project. Thank you, Marlaine, for setting me up for success. Special thanks to my family, especially to my husband, Craig Siefert, for your unwavering sentiments of love and encouragement over the last few years. It is because of your continued engagement and support that I am able to celebrate this academic achievement.

BACKGROUND

In the convenient care or ambulatory care setting, the management of the patient versus the customer becomes one integrated concept. Health care organizations utilize best practice models based in service recovery to handle and respond to concerns that arise following a patient visit to the clinic (Sarel & Marmorstein, 1999). This doctoral project sought to improve the trends of patient concerns through prevention and management at the initial point of interaction between the providers, nurse practitioners and licensed vocational nurses, and the patient. Implementation of face to face educational training as a quality improvement measure was intended to strengthen the health care provider's ability to satisfy the delicate patient-customer balance that exists in the ambulatory care delivery environment.

With the recent downturn of the U.S. economy, Americans have been confronted with multi-faceted challenges including job insecurity, increased cost of living, and unknowns about the future. One particular arena impacted greatly by the strained economy is healthcare. In addition to rising healthcare costs, there is a projected shortage of the primary care providers, which in turn affects access to healthcare (Cheng, 2012). The idea of improving access to primary care is not a new one and has been extensively discussed in the literature (Cheng, 2012; Hansen-Turton, Ware, & McClellan, 2010; Zand, 2011).

Over ten years ago, a shift to a new model of care delivery, the convenient care model, emerged to provide rapid and convenient access to care for local communities in response to these trends. Convenient care clinics (CCCs) are typically staffed by nurse practitioners and physician assistants and located most commonly within larger retail

stores or pharmacies. CCCs offer convenient high-quality medical care, treat minor illnesses as well as providing chronic illness screening and monitoring, and, through cost transparency, are substantially more affordable options for the busy consumer (Hansen-Turton, Ridgway, Ryan, & Nash, 2009). This option of healthcare delivery improves access to care and has been well received by the public (Evans, 2010).

Part of the growing success of CCCs is the larger managing organizations' focus on patient-centered care which stretches traditional definitions to include meeting the needs of the patient as the consumer of healthcare and placing emphasis on patient satisfaction (Berry & Mirabito, 2010). Research studies and healthcare industry efforts over the last decade have trended towards the topic of patient satisfaction and its impact on quality of care, patient loyalty, and patient outcomes (Needham, 2012). From a national perspective, the U.S. government also values the important role of the consumer, recently passing laws to reward facilities that achieve high patient satisfaction ratings (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2012).

Needs Assessment

Understanding the patient's perspective about their healthcare experience and being able to report data to stakeholders and insurance payors has triggered the implementation of patient satisfaction surveys by many healthcare organizations (Otani et al., 2009). The Centers for Medicare and Medicaid (CMS) collects and reports information related to quality of care across health care settings with a future goal of reimbursing health care organizations based partly on these quality of care measures (Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services, 2012). Currently, patient satisfaction data in

the form of healthcare report cards are readily available for access to the consumer via the internet (Ford & Fottler, 2000).

Despite the wealth of easily accessible survey data, researchers continue to further explore the root cause of what factors most impact patient satisfaction and how such information ought to be evaluated and used to maximize the patient experience. The need to revisit the effectiveness of structured satisfaction surveys' singular role in bringing about practice change comes from evidence suggesting that their lack of specificity presents a barrier to the identification of actual issues (Reeves & Seccombe, 2008). Alternate measures for identifying issues such as close patient concern monitoring are therefore necessary to identify specific patient or customer related concerns for the purposes of driving organizational quality improvement efforts. Based on the need for continuous quality improvement in patient care, the Centre for Clinical Governance at the University of New South Wales performed a comprehensive literature review in 2009 that looked at patient satisfaction and complaints research. They concluded there is a general lack of process change occurring in healthcare settings and that the minimal use of patient survey data may be a contributing factor (Centre for Clinical Governance, 2009). The literature review also demonstrates that complaints data can and should be used in quality improvement efforts as complaints have been shown to drive change as compared to satisfaction data alone (Centre for Clinical Governance, 2009). Once trends are understood, interventions that aim to prevent patient concerns can be initiated. Such preventive approaches can occur at the clinician level with the goal of optimizing the clinician's skill set in early recognition and identification of potential concerns related to any aspect of the patient care experience.

Currently, the process in the writer's organization for reporting concerns related to any aspect of the clinical visit involves the patient calling a central call center whereby the patient's concern is documented, filed, and categorized. Managers then review the concern, respond to the patient by phone and review the case with the provider involved to determine the context of the concern. Complaint handling in this manner is common to many large organizations and health care systems (Peate & Walsh, 2010). Razali and Jaafar (2012) proposed a theoretical framework for the handling of complaints that requires a method of access to file concerns first and foremost. The suggested response process is then to offer an apology, provide an explanation, and ensure a quality resolution (Razali & Jaafar, 2012). While the established complaints handling process is necessary and an important component of extending patient-centered care beyond the clinic visit encounter, it is a reactive process.

In the convenient care or ambulatory care setting, there is a need to empower the providers at the front lines of patient care. Development of the delivery of optimal customer service served as the central theme of this quality improvement project. The provider's ability to anticipate and address all aspects of care, whether clinical, environmental, or financial in nature, stands to strengthen the provider-patient relationship as well as the patient's overall customer service experience. Transitioning providers to anticipate common patient or customer related concerns supports the establishment of a proactive process. This quality improvement was implemented in response to a need for improving the incidence of customer concerns called in by patients who visit the convenient care clinics supervised by the writer. Furthermore, a recent

annual provider survey demonstrated that the ability to address customer service problems was a specific item in need of improvement throughout the organization.

Purpose Statement

This project aimed to empower the nurse practitioner or licensed vocational nurse provider in the convenient care or ambulatory care setting through a series of face to face inservices that teach preventive approaches employed during patient-customer interactions for the purposes of mitigating patient concerns before they occur.

The following questions were proposed by this quality improvement project:

1. Will designing a provider training program based on research on customer satisfaction in healthcare empower the nurse or advanced nurse provider to better address and anticipate patient concerns before they occur?
2. Can the rate and type of customer concerns received in the ambulatory care setting be improved by enhancing the ability of the nurse or advanced nurse at the clinic level to address and anticipate patient concerns before they occur?

Supporting Framework

Nadler and Gerstein's (1992) theoretical framework on high-performance work systems (HPWS) provides a basis for organizations that link together factors of "empowerment, trust . . . training, [and] teamwork" (Nadler & Gerstein as cited by Scotti, Harman, & Behson, 2007, p. 111). Traditionally, HPWS has been utilized by human resource and management departments to create positive, supportive work atmospheres for the employee (Lowe, 2002). Employee retention, loyalty, and work productivity have been demonstrated in the literature as outcomes of HPWS implementation (Lowe, 2002). In 2007, Scotti et al. took Nadler and Gerstein's HPWS framework and translated it into

the healthcare setting, tying together the pieces of high-performance with customer service, customer orientation, loyalty, and satisfaction. Scotti et al.'s (2007) landmark study was the first to “empirically [verify] the entire chain of effects from organizational practices to service quality to customer satisfaction in a healthcare setting” (p. 119). The author suggests that this model, which was studied in the ambulatory care setting, can be expanded to most healthcare settings. Empowering the employee by building confidence in their customer service skills influences the employee’s “perceptions of high-quality service” which, in turn, has been “linked with customer satisfaction” (Scotti et al., 2007, p. 109). The high-performance work systems framework guided the purpose of this quality improvement project which invested in the training and support of the customer service-oriented nurse practitioner and licensed vocational nurse in the convenient care health setting. The expectation was to find a relationship between the provider’s improved service approach and the patient’s perception of their clinical experience.

A MENTOR Framework

Steinman (2013) blames a deficiency in customer service training as the reason for patient concerns in healthcare and highlights the “B.L.A.S.T. technique” developed by Albert Barneto in 2009. BLAST stands for “Believe, Listen, Apologize, Satisfy, and Thank” and was designed as a tool to support healthcare providers with managing a patient presenting with complaints or concerns (Steinman, 2013, p. 25). Steinman (2013) recommends further research that might quantify whether or not teaching behavioral methods like BLAST will improve the patient clinical experience.

Based on Barneto’s (2009) technique and Steinman’s recommendations (2013), a similar technique has been developed for this quality improvement project. The thematic

acronym referred to as A MENTOR differs from the BLAST technique in that it prepares the clinician to foresee and deal with all aspects of the patient's clinical experience at the point of the first patient encounter before a concern or complaint is generated. A MENTOR was used as a guiding principle for the development of this quality improvement project's education and training sessions.

HPWS serves as the grand framework for empowering the healthcare provider in the extent to which their interactions maximizes the patient's customer service experience and in turn drives a self-motivated interest in delivering service that will translate into positive patient feedback. The BLAST framework helps to narrow the focus of this project by providing tools and a strong basis upon which the A MENTOR framework and its behavior related components were developed. Ultimately, A MENTOR functions as the strict framework which guides this quality improvement project. Empowering providers in the ambulatory care setting to proactively handle potential patient concerns calls upon the providers to:

- Anticipate and address expectations
- Manage the patient as a customer
- Establish rapport
- Negotiate and partner
- Treat the clinical and customer diagnoses
- Offer clarification as needed
- Recognize concerns and reinforce realistic solutions and expectations

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Search Methods

A review of the literature was conducted in preparation for the development of this quality improvement project. The following electronic databases were searched for publications relevant to the topics of patient satisfaction and patient concerns: CINAHL, PubMed, Academic Search Premier, PsychInfo, and Google Scholar. MeSH terms were also used and included patient satisfaction, customer complaints, complaints handling. Further search terms included patient-centered care, patient satisfaction and quality of care, and customer service in healthcare. Peer-reviewed journal publications represented the majority of the articles selected for review. Reference lists of retrieved documents were also hand searched to identify pertinent publications.

Patient Satisfaction

Consumer satisfaction models have been utilized by the service industry for years to increase business via consumer loyalty. Falkenreck and Wagner (2011) evaluated the relationship between innovative health care marketing and the consumer and “confirm[ed] cross culturally the widely accepted theory that there is a link between satisfaction and loyalty” (p. 235). Falkenreck and Wagner’s (2011) findings are supported throughout the literature which suggests that competitive trends in the healthcare industry call for a push in the direction toward consumer satisfaction (Ford & Fottler, 2000; Needham, 2012; Talib, Rhaman, & Azam, 2011). This form of healthy competition has also been heavily spurred on by the Centers of Medicare and Medicaid’s Consumer Assessment of Health Providers and Systems (CAHPS) surveys which consider the patient’s consumer perspective to gain insight into aspects of care that are

uniquely important to the patient (CMS, 2012). Ford and Fottler (2000), for example, discuss opportunities for creating a new customer-focused paradigm that encourages patient participation, customer training for providers, a welcoming environment, and continued improvement efforts driven by the consumer's expectations. These ideas echo Needham (2012) who also believes that the healthcare industry can reference and learn from familiar corporate practices already in play in restaurant, hotel, airline, and car dealership chains (Ford & Fottler, 2000).

Patient satisfaction as a function of quality care must first be defined before plans are implemented to improve such outcomes. Alrubaiee and Alkaa'ida (2011) define patient satisfaction as "an emotional response" that is based on patient expectations, past experiences and overall attitude towards a particular healthcare encounter (p. 106). From an application standpoint, Suhonen et al. (2011) demonstrate the role of individualized nursing as a method of improving patient satisfaction in the hospital setting, linking satisfaction to quality and patient-centered approaches. Suhonen et al. (2011) recommend that individualized patient care can be extrapolated to the primary clinical care environment.

It is already known that patient satisfaction ratings are exceptionally high and that care rendered by family nurse practitioners employed in CCCs is valued by the public (see Appendix E, Table 1) (Evans, 2010; Hunter, Weber, Morreale, & Wall, 2009). Studies of convenient care clinics also demonstrate that quality of care rendered is in line with primary care and urgent care settings and that providers treat in accordance with national practice guidelines (see Appendix E, Table 1) (Mehrota et al., 2009; Woodburn, Smith, & Nelson, 2007). However, with the growing expansion and popularity of

convenient care clinics throughout the United States, the need to ensure that quality of care is not only upheld but also continually improved is crucial to their continued success (Keckley, Underwood, & Ghandi, 2008). Consequently, it makes sense to look for ways to enhance customer service efforts in the ambulatory convenient care setting in order to reinforce consumer trust and provide a positive patient experience.

Patient Perception and Provider Relationships

How patients perceive their clinical experience influences their degree of satisfaction upon discharge (see Appendix E, Table 2) (Alrubaiee & Alkaa'ida, 2011). In addition, the quality of the patient's relationship with the provider may determine their perception of the clinical encounter and vice versa. Epstein et al.'s (2005) research on patient-centered communication (PCC) between healthcare providers, patients, and families sought to better understand the four domains that encompass PCC (see Appendix E, Table 2). The four areas associated with PCC include the understanding of the patient's perspective of care, recognizing psychosocial factors at play, achieving a shared viewpoint of the presenting problem, and ensuring a shared responsibility with respect to plan of care and solution seeking (p. 1517). Iacobucci, Ostrom, and Grayson (1995) bring together the patient's perception, communication and satisfaction, stating that "customer satisfaction is a function of the discrepancy between a consumer's prior expectations and his or her perception regarding the purchase" (p. 278). This concept rooted in consumer psychology principles plays into each patient encounter in the retail health care setting.

The topic of "Customer Satisfaction in Health Care" is addressed further by Reisberg (1996) who teaches that acceptance of the patient as a customer is the first step

to empowering providers to achieve best patient-care models and relationships (Boutary, 2012). “Everyone is a customer” (Reisberg, 1996, p. 12), and “professional behavior should make it clear that [the provider is] working in the best interest of customers...[as the] intent is to battle for consumers, not against them” (p. 12). Reisberg (1996) suggests that meeting the patient’s basic needs which can include offering a sense of security, control, providing recognition, as well as fairness in treatment, creates an environment of trust. In doing so, the patient-provider relationship transforms into a partnership. Needham’s (2012) take on the “truth about the patient experience” (p. 255) is summarized into a proposed framework referred to as the “three P’s: personalize medicine, partner with patients, and empower employees” (p. 259). Needham (2012) states that total management of the patient in the healthcare setting begins with the healthcare provider who must first recognize the unique psychosocial and physical aspects of each patient experience and address all concerns at every patient encounter.

Patient Concerns

While patient satisfaction is typically evaluated by structured surveys, the specific experience of the patient as the individual may not be adequately represented by such measurements alone. Patient satisfaction surveys assess a general impression of a clinical experience averaging data derived from structured response scales (Reeves & Seccombe, 2008). Achieving “excellence” in patient satisfaction should be the goal in healthcare at both the manager and provider levels, not average (Otani et al., 2009). While the average survey scores give an overall impression, an avenue by which specific concerns are voiced may provide insight on particular patient needs, trends, and issues which typically fall beyond the scope of a survey.

It is already known that positive patient experiences may positively effect patient outcomes (Pichert, Hickson, & Moore, 2008). A study in England about attitudes towards and barriers with use of surveys in health care also highlighted the connection between patient satisfaction and patient-centered care (Reeves & Seccombe, 2008). In order to be able to capitalize on valuable patient feedback, it appears that tools beyond the structured survey may be needed in the healthcare setting. Davies and Cleary (2005) confirm the shortcoming of surveys with respect to quality improvement noting that “healthcare organisations need to develop cultures that support patient centred care, quality improvement capacity, [and] professional receptiveness and leadership , . . . [but that] the surveys themselves do not indicate what needs to be done to improve any situation” (p. 432). Further strengthening Davies and Cleary’s (2005) perspective, Hsieh (2012) suggests that surveys “passively report patient views” (p. 471), neglecting to fully “capture [the patient’s] voice in full” (p. 471) in her research on categorizing and collecting patient concern data in the hospital setting (see Appendix E, Table 3).

According to Hsieh (2012) and others (Davies & Cleary, 2005; Pichert et al., 2008) more research should be focused on individual patient complaints because concrete details and patterns of concerns allow for implementation of specific preventive interventions that aim to improve processes and reduce future occurrences. Blakemore (2013) recently investigated criticism from health officials pertaining to issues with the handling of patient concerns. In particular, Blakemore (2013) highlighted comments made by an ombudsman involved in a particular hospital case who states that “hospitals aren’t using complaints as the vital source of feedback they are. Learning from patients, improving services and building trust all flow from managing complaints effectively” (p.

5). In 2010, Painter addressed the importance of nurses' ability in understanding patient concerns through her work with renal patients requiring dialysis. After investigating the common concerns that drive a dialysis patient to decline arteriovenous fistula (AVF) placement, she discovered, that effective communication can be accomplished given the right tools, and that ultimately, these principles can be implemented into any healthcare setting. Effective communication, however, does not occur spontaneously and requires a deeper understanding of the patient's perception of the interaction.

Stickler and Schumacher (2003) best review the concept of the value of patient concerns in their article entitled "The Gift of Customer Complaints" which attempts to shift traditional healthcare views that patient complaints are failures, and instead, points out that complaints can be used by healthcare professionals as opportunities for corrective, even preventive action. Therefore, organizations are responsible to train their employees effectively to recognize and understand a customer's expectations in order for employees, or in this case, healthcare providers, to be able to "manage their behavior appropriately to match their customers' underlying expectations" (Gruber, Szmigin, & Voss, 2009, p. 638).

Empowering the Service-Oriented Nurse Practitioner

Extensive search of health related literature provides insight into the importance of complaints handling and reveals several recommendations for interventions at the clinician level. Painter (2010) concluded that "with good communication and effective tools, nurses can learn the reason behind each . . . patient's concerns and begin to develop strategies to minimize the potentially negative effects of these concerns" (p. 471).

Similar to continuous clinical education expected of all licensed healthcare providers, additional, continuous pathways of practitioner training in customer service should be considered, which go beyond the initial new hire orientation training common to many healthcare institutions. Needham's (2012) third "P," the empowerment of employees, is likely the most important piece to achieving satisfaction and preventing customer concerns, as employees are "the best suited to improve the patient experience" (p. 261). For the purposes of this quality improvement project, the family nurse practitioner or licensed vocational nurse's role in mitigating customer experience concerns and maximizing satisfaction might be considered the hypothetical fourth "P," prevention. As a result, implementing specific strategies to support medical professionals' ability to service the patient-customer and deliver a complete and positive experience at every visit has been recommended as a next step in the literature. For example, Ammentorp, Kofoed, and Laulund (2010) conducted a study in the pediatric setting that looked at the impact of communication skills training of healthcare providers on patients' perceptions of care. They found that a training workshop using provider role play tactics resulted in statistically significant improvement of the patients' perception of quality of care rendered. Ammentorp et al. (2010) state that "understanding patients' concerns, needs, [and] expectations ... should be regarded as an important element of patient-centered care" (p. 398) and as such, served as the foundation of the employee education course.

Twelve years prior to the Ammentorp et al. (2010) study, Mayer, Cates, Mastorovich, and Royalty (1998) also looked at the influence of customer service training within the hospital emergency department setting, and assessed patient

satisfaction ratings of clinicians' skills (see Appendix E, Table 3). Their intervention entailed eight hours of customer service training broken up into modules to achieve three core competencies: "making the customer service diagnosis ... and providing treatment," "negotiating agreement resolution of patient expectations," and "building moments of truth into the clinical encounter" (p. 2). They found that patient complaints surrounding negative staff attitudes and rude communication decreased following intensive staff training. Patient satisfaction scores also improved.

Education for Empowerment

Development of an effective teaching strategy that aims to empower the healthcare provider calls for consideration of the type of learner, setting for education instruction, and delivery modalities and strategies. Adult learners with a health professions background respond well to lecture, role play, and case scenarios based methods of teaching (Bradshaw & Lowenstein, 2014). While lecture formats provide structure to the session and are led mostly by the instructor, the subsequent strategies open up the opportunity for interaction, idea sharing, and feedback. Reconstructing real-life based patient cases or encounters promotes engagement of the adult learner who holds experience in the field (Bradshaw & Lowenstein, 2014). The instructor is then tasked with developing a curriculum that the experienced adult learner can relate to within the classroom setting with the goal of informing, stimulating, and ultimately fueling a behavior change in the professional environment as a result.

Changing clinician behavior has been explored in the literature. Grimshaw, Eccles, Walker, and Thomas (2002) speak to the factors that affect the extent to which a physician will respond to implementation of new organizational processes or changes to

processes. Following multiple systematic reviews, the researchers found that “passive dissemination” of educational materials in isolation is the least effective strategy for prompting behavioral changes and call for “active approaches” and “multifaceted interventions” that may involve periodic repetition and revisiting in order to propel maintenance of change (Grimshaw et al., 2002, p. 239). A similar review by Grol and Grimshaw (2003) suggest that while continuous education materials or sessions are useful in imparting evidenced based information to healthcare providers, transforming practice and building professional development occurs best when education is integrated into daily patient care routines, is interactive, and invites feedback and reminders (p. 1228).

A study by Lampe, Coulston, Walter, and Malhi (2010) identified methods of effective teaching for medical psychiatry students facing clinical rotations with close patient interactions. They found that students preferred in-person clinically focused education sessions that were taught using a structured learning model (Lampe et al., 2010). Skills were also reinforced a few times per week with one on one support from the instructor, which the authors believe played a key part in the students’ education. This form of face to face instruction allowed students the opportunity to provide and receive feedback in real time. Although the study was limited to the field of psychiatry, the teaching principles reflect the training approaches already discussed in the Ammentorp et al. (2010) and Mayer et al. (1998) research studies.

Considerations and Stakeholders

Patient concerns can be called in by anyone related to the patient. Patient privacy is protected by requesting verbal permission from the patient first prior to discussing any

clinic visit related information with the individual who actually is calling in the concern. The call center resource phone number is provided to all patients that present to the clinic for a visit. Practitioners involved in the A MENTOR training are required to attend staff meetings monthly as part of their role expectation and ongoing agency credentialing. The implementing any quality improvement piece that educates staff members is decided at the management's discretion as needs arise.

Managers, clinicians, patients, and the agency where this quality improvement project was carried out are considered the stakeholders. Managers and the agency are key stakeholders due to the innate investment in the improvement of the patient experience in their convenient care clinics. Patients, the agency's clients, are also stakeholders as they were the ultimate recipients of the changes generated by the A MENTOR training.

PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION METHODS

This quality improvement project based in research focused on the prevention of patient and consumer concerns using face to face education sessions that included interactive teaching strategies through lecture and case studies, as well as role play opportunities and field level reinforcement to elevate the customer service skills of the nurse practitioner and licensed vocational nurse in the ambulatory care setting. Adequate training of the aforementioned providers involved in this project prepares and empowers them through confidence building around a skill not otherwise taught through conventional nursing education.

This quality improvement project began with an exploration of categorical trends of patient concerns reported in the retail health care setting in order to develop a structured educational format that was rooted in genuine patient scenarios facing the providers on a regular basis. Items from organizational annual surveys that spoke to comfort level with customer service related needs of the patients in the convenient care setting were identified as an area of needed improvement. Manager experience with current patient concern handling helped to identify the most frequently encountered category of concerns that warranted the most attention for this quality improvement project. Anecdotal evidence shared by providers and licensed vocational nurses during routine field rounds as well as common questions asked of managers also guided the development of the customer service based curriculum. In addition, surveys were distributed prior to the initial staff meeting which addressed the first topic about insurance and billing concerns. Responses gathered from those surveys were reviewed and served as the foundation for how subsequent patient concern topics would be

presented. The feedback received in these surveys are discussed in the Results section of this report.

The initial plan for this quality improvement project had focused on the family nurse practitioner in the convenient care clinic setting. However, after spending several days per week coaching and rounding at clinics training and orienting recently hired licensed vocational nurses in our practice setting, it became apparent that comfort level with the customer service piece of the role would be just as valuable for the licensed vocational nurses (LVNs) as it would be for the nurse practitioners (NPs). The LVNs would be the first point of contact for most patients seeking care within the walk-in clinic model and would be performing tasks in all customer service areas inclusive of billing and insurance, managing patients waiting, and some basic clinical support to the nurse practitioners such as post diagnosis and plan of care reinforcement. Patient satisfaction and the potential for preventing customer concerns are driven by the entire patient experience that may begin with the LVN provider who welcomes patients into the clinic and prepares them to see the nurse practitioner. After a thorough review of customer concern trends and weighing the role of the LVNs as the first encounter point with the patient, the decision was made to provide training to both the LVNs and NPs as well as collect feedback through the aforementioned surveys. All nurse practitioners and licensed vocational nurses among the twelve clinics located in the Southwestern part of the United States received training during routine staff meetings.

Sequence, Setting, and Resources

The volume of customer concerns data appears to increase during the busier fall and winter months which are generally regarded as cold and flu season. Preparing

providers, both nurse practitioners and licensed vocational nurses in this ambulatory care setting to better manage and prevent concerns in anticipation of the busier season determined the seasonal timing of this project's implementation. Nurse practitioners and licensed vocational nurses attended a thirty minute face to face in-service focused on best practices when managing the patient as a customer. The sequential in-services were held once a month for four months in October 2013, November 2013, January 2014, and February 2014 and incorporated into routine mandatory monthly staff meetings. Staff meetings routinely are deferred in the month of December due to end of year alternate time commitment demands of managers and providers. Each training session focused on the concept that patient or customer concerns are preventable. Providers were taught to recognize patients as customers, to enhance communication skills, to set expectations with respect to the whole patient encounter, to negotiate as needed, and to reinforce skills in managing any visit related concerns that might present at the time of the encounter.

Resources needed for the implementation of this project were limited to a thirty minute time slot dedicated during each of the two hour staff meetings to A MENTOR training. No additional costs or time was required of the providers or the managers in support of this project as the sessions were incorporated into already scheduled staff team meetings; providers in attendance are routinely paid for work related meetings which are required and budgeted for in advance.

In-Service Structure and Content

Methods of instruction were chosen based on the needs of the adult professional learner and included lecture via a Microsoft Powerpoint slide show presentation, case scenarios, and role play (Bradshaw & Lowenstein, 2014). The presentation followed a

lecture format as topics were introduced primarily for the purposes of providing rationale through evidence-based literature prior to moving into the case scenarios and role play activities. Each session was conducted by a family nurse practitioner who holds a management position. Case scenarios were based on the three common concern themes including billing, clinical, and facility factors such as wait times and crowd management. A customer service emphasis and tone was integrated into all topics and related talking points. It is important to note that based on manager experience in responding to these concerns, the categories often overlap. For example, a billing concern may be interwoven with a clinical issue raised by the patient, or an excessive wait time may impact the patient's perception of the quality of care rendered. Therefore, each subsequent session of training reinforced topics presented at sessions prior for the purposes of connecting the individual segments of the patient visit into one whole big picture understanding.

Determining the sequence of each training session was based on two important factors: the sequence of the patient experience in this particular ambulatory care setting and the frequency of the concerns received based on filed category. The typical patient visit begins with a registration process that addresses cost of service, medical insurance processing, and a plan for payment due at end of visit. Based on management's experience, most concerns despite their categorization, are tied to the patient's perceived monetary value and understanding of the cost of services offered. This is the first topic addressed at the beginning of every patient visit or encounter whether it is initiated by the LVN or the NP. In addition, the billing and payment aspect of the role, although taught during orientation, is not taught during nursing school and tends to be an "on the job"

learning process for most providers. Anecdotally, providers, especially recent new hires, have verbalized challenges around explaining insurance, payment, and coverage to patients, admitting a limited comfort level.

A MENTOR Session 1

Therefore, the first training session which took place at the October 2013 staff meeting focused on utilizing the A MENTOR framework for preventing billing related concerns. This session took place at the October 2013 staff meeting. Being that this was the providers' first exposure to the A MENTOR framework, time was taken to provide background into the importance of patient satisfaction in healthcare, the specific role of patient concerns, and the need to ensure full patient understanding before the visit even begins. Proposed talking points were mapped out based on the A MENTOR structure and the provider-patient discussion about the billing process was broken down into related segments. The lead instructor demonstrated the role of the nurse professional as well as the possible responses from the patient. At the end, two case scenarios were presented and a short five minute time frame remained for group role play. Appendix A highlights the detail talking points that were presented for preventing billing concerns utilizing the A MENTOR structure as a guide.

A MENTOR Session 2

The second training session in November 2013 focused on ways to mitigate concerns patients may have regarding clinical aspects of care. This in-service began with a recap of the A MENTOR framework and followed a similar slide presentation format. Talking points and tools presented equipped the practitioners and nurses in achieving full patient understanding of their presenting medical condition and treatment plan. A nurse

practitioner was invited to perform a role play with the instructor based on the talking points available to demonstrate what the interaction would look like pursuant to the A MENTOR framework. The patient's comprehension of their clinical picture and the extent to which their expectations were met or exceeded by the health care provider effects their perception of the quality of the visit (Baron-Epel, Dushenat, & Friedman, 2001). The emphasis of this session was to teach both the nurse practitioners and the licensed vocational nurses to not underestimate the importance of educating patients about their diagnosis and plan, and to do so in a fashion that is easy for the patient to understand. If the patient does not buy into the diagnosis and plan of care, the risk exists that the patient may not adhere to recommendations made. This session also reinforced existing tools readily accessible at the clinic level to support successful communication so that clinical expectations from the viewpoint of the patient are made clear and realistic. Several years prior to this quality improvement project, the agency put into practice the routine use of the Ask Me 3®, a health literacy tool created by the National Patient Safety Foundation (NPSF). NPSF describes Ask Me 3® as "a patient education program designed to improve communication between patients and health care providers, encourage patients to become active members of their health care team, and promote improved health outcomes" (NPSF, 2014, para. 1). Patients are encouraged to ask and understand the answers to the following three questions: "What is my main problem?; What do I need to do?; Why is it important for me to do this?" (NPSF, 2014, para 1). The tool is available free for the use of health care agencies for purposes of stressing the importance of patient safety and literacy. The A MENTOR framework integrates the principles of Ask Me 3® to further the quality of the patient's clinical experience and

strengthen the confidence of the nurse practitioner and licensed vocational nurse during each visit.

A MENTOR Session 3

The third A MENTOR in-service held in January 2014 was structured around handling potential facility concerns such as wait times, hours of operation, and miscellaneous general customer service concerns. While a slide show presentation was utilized and a brief review of A MENTOR initiated this in-service, the role play strategy was placed at the start of this session and a licensed vocational nurse was selected to work through a patient scenario related to wait times and crowd management. Feedback from providers in attendance were welcomed and best practices on how to manage facility related patient questions for the prevention of concerns and maximization of satisfaction were discussed in an open forum format. The instructor then returned the discussion back to a lecture format for purposes of demonstrating that the open discussion identified talking points outlined in the slides.

A MENTOR Session 4

The fourth session served as a brief recap of the A MENTOR process of preventing patient concerns. This session was not originally planned for but added due to lower than expected attendance at the January staff meeting. Due to holidays, the month of December did not have a scheduled staff meeting and the project lead wanted to ensure that the number of meeting attendees was optimized and exposed to a full review of A MENTOR prior to completion of the post educational feedback survey. Due to conflicting commitments, the fourth recap session was led by a manager colleague who is also a family nurse practitioner and has been closely involved with the goals of this

quality improvement project as well as supportive of encouraging this approach at the clinic level. This session lasted fifteen minutes and was designed as a review that hit the highlights of A MENTOR and invited a dialogue around recent encounters from the field related to any aspect of the customer service experience. A post training survey was distributed at this final meeting.

All staff received the A MENTOR educational materials presented at each staff meeting the following day by email. Email communication of information shared at the monthly staff meetings is conventionally sent out to team members in this fashion. The NPs and LVNs were encouraged to practice what they had learned after each session and role play with their respective clinic partners utilizing the talking points presented and case scenarios reviewed.

PROJECT EVALUATION

Evaluation Methods

Survey evaluation methods were used to determine practitioner confidence levels around billing, facility, clinical, and customer service related patient needs. Surveys in the form of pencil and paper questionnaires were distributed before and after in-service sessions to assess the provider's self-perceived view of their ease in driving patient satisfaction based on these themes. Kelley, Clark, Brown, and Sitzia (2003) describe the ideal questionnaire layout as being well organized with questions numbered and grouped by topic. A combination of closed ended and open ended questions produces different kinds of information and added value. Kelley et al. (2003) note that although open ended questions require more time and thought of the respondent, a well written open ended question can evoke deeper meaning and insight into the topic of interest. For this quality improvement project, questions were constructed to gain a better understanding of NP and LVN customer service related comfort level and to discern common themes that present challenges to the providers. In the interest of maintaining anonymity and objectivity, the surveys were provided at the start of the staff meeting as nurse practitioners and licensed vocational nurses arrive and at the end of the final session as team members were exiting. The impact of this quality improvement project was evaluated using surveys distributed before the initiation of the A MENTOR educational series and after the series completion.

Pre In-Service Survey Structure

In the first phase of evaluation, providers completed a questionnaire prior to their customer service training to assess the level of comfort they had with this aspect of their

role in healthcare. The pre in-service survey was comprised of nine questions (see Appendix C). The first question was for identification purposes only and asked if the individual is a nurse practitioner or licensed vocational nurse. The second, fourth, sixth, and eighth questions addressed the concern categories as previously discussed using a 5-point Likert scale to determine comfort level in each area of customer service. The alternate questions, numbers three, five, seven, and nine were open-ended to allow for responses that might elicit specific examples by which future sessions may make the effort of addressing. Of 35 attendees at the staff meeting, 32 responses were collected prior to beginning the in-service. Assimilation and evaluation of the survey responses occurred in the weeks following this initial meeting in order to prepare for the following three in-services scheduled for November 2013, January 2014, and February 2014.

Post In-Service Survey Structure

In the post education phase of evaluation, providers completed a questionnaire at the end of the fourth and final customer service training session to determine their level of comfort and confidence with managing potential patient concerns following their exposure to the A MENTOR framework. The post in-service survey was comprised of seven questions (see Appendix D). Questions two through five addressed the potential billing, clinical, facility and general customer service concern categories using a 5-point Likert scale to determine comfort level in each area. The questions were written in a manner that cued the NPs and LVNs to think about their responses after the completion of A MENTOR training. The subsequent questions, numbered six and seven were open ended and asked about behavior changes or modifications in the way practice would be conducted after the knowledge gained through this education.

Survey Response Evaluation

Survey responses were collected and manually entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet to facilitate review and analysis. Average overall respondent scores were calculated for each closed ended, Likert-scale style question asked. Average scores were also calculated for the NP respondents alone and then for the LVN respondents. Open ended responses from the pre in-service questionnaire were evaluated for thematic commonalities and that information was integrated into the clinical, facility, and wrap up sessions.

Ongoing and Future Evaluation

The expectation is that A MENTOR will serve as a permanent framework by which new hires and current staff can apply this approach when faced with unfamiliar situations or organizational transitions that require skilled communication and teaching strategies. As managers and leaders continue to review patient concern trends and satisfaction rates, A MENTOR can be revisited during future field rounds, provider coaching and again at a larger scale at staff meetings. In terms of expanded evaluation plans, patient concern rates, patient satisfaction scores, and general customer service trends are being continually considered and analyzed to determine whether a measurable effect exists due to A MENTOR training. For proprietary reasons, this data did not comprise a segment of this final report. However, its value is recognized and remains internally reviewed.

RESULTS

Field Observations

Following the initial A MENTOR training session, the presentation and talking points were emailed out to the entire group of nurse practitioners and licensed vocational nurses to ensure all providers not only were able to review the presentation, but also able to reference learning materials for reinforcement at the clinic level. Positive feedback was offered from several NPs and LVNs immediately following the meeting. The NPs noted that presenting A MENTOR with an evidence-based background was most impactful. One LVN noted that the timing of the billing and insurance A MENTOR piece was in line with real life practice challenges. This particular LVN printed the slide presentation and reviewed it with their NP counterpart in a role play format the following day.

Field rounding followed each A MENTOR training session and is a routine strategy for encouraging needed behavior change in response to new initiatives occurring organizationally. Coaching providers at the clinic sites to reinforce each topic presented on A MENTOR occurred regularly. Area managers supported the reinforcement of principles learned as well in order to reach each clinic location. Observing visits and debriefing with both the NPs and LVNs opened up opportunities for further discussion of best practices and talking points that might help facilitate a presenting patient satisfaction challenge in the moment. The additional benefit of the field rounds allowed for real time role play, open question and answer sessions and the chance to discuss what providers perceive as their most challenging patient encounters scenarios. Providers visited were

identified based on managers' awareness of recent patient concern trends, being newer to the organization, and those requesting more support in the area of patient satisfaction.

Following the second A MENTOR session, behavioral changes at the clinic level were observed. One outcome that stood out following the clinically focused A MENTOR session was the deliberate effort of displaying the Ask Me 3® tool brochures and logos in new locations in the clinic. Notably, the Ask Me 3® logo was attached to computer screens or isolated in a separate area near to where the patient is typically situated during a visit (see Appendix B). When providers were asked about this change, both the NPs and LVNs stated that the A MENTOR session that discussed clinical expectations of patients reminded them of the value of this tool and how it will help them ensure patient understanding of the care plan and diagnosis prior to leaving the clinic.

Comfort level with managing patients waiting to be seen, kiosk sign in process challenges, expectations around break times, and end of day closing procedures was also reinforced at the clinic level during manager-led rounds. Best practices such as maintaining an active awareness of visit length times, list of patients signed in and how to identify crowd frustrations were reviewed. Overall, providers noted that the teams that communicated the best with each other tended to report more confidence and skill in handling the flow of patients and managing wait time expectations. Following the completion of all the A MENTOR session, LVNs and NPs requested that challenging real-life case scenarios are presented either at future staff meetings or by internal email communication with the A MENTOR framework outlined as a reminder process with preventive solutions suggested in the body of the message. On a systems level, the concept behind A MENTOR is under consideration for implementation in the form of an

organizational accepted competency for high level performers in the area of customer service.

Pre In-Service Survey

Twenty-four completed questionnaires were obtained from the providers attending the initial in-service in November 2013. These were distributed prior to the introduction of the A MENTOR framework. Of the 24 surveys, twenty were completed by family nurse practitioners (NPs) and four were completed by licensed vocational nurses (LVNs).

The average overall survey score out of a total of 5 possible was 4.38 for the whole group (n = 24). This score represented the general confidence level of both nurse practitioners and licensed vocational nurses in addressing patient concerns across all categories: billing, facility, clinical and empathy. For managing billing concerns alone, the average score among the twenty-four providers was 4.04, the lowest score across all categories. Confidence level around facility related concerns was 4.29 on average and 4.33 for confidence managing clinical related expectations. Comfort level with empathy and active listening was high at a mean of 4.83. The family nurse practitioners (n = 20) reported an average confidence level of 4.39 across all categories related to customer service. The licensed vocational nurses (n = 4) reported an average confidence level of 4.31.

Addressing and managing patient expectations around billing and insurance issues scored lowest among all customer service related topics by both the NPs and the LVNs, 4.10 and 3.75, respectively. Confidence around managing facility issues was next with a mean of 4.30 for the NPs and 4.25 for the LVNs. Managing clinical expectations was

rated on average at 4.35 for the NPs and 4.25 for the LVNs. Interestingly, the LVNs rated their ability to actively listen and empathize higher than the NPs. Both the NPs and LVNs reported this area as their highest comfort area in customer service. Due to group size discrepancies between the NPs and LVNs, differences in groups were not measurable.

Themes were identified based on nurse practitioner and licensed vocational nurse responses to the open ended questions that prompted a narrative response related to each of the common areas of patient concerns. With respect to comfort level with managing billing and insurance expectations, the most frequent theme that emerged was the challenge in correctly identifying the correct insurance plan in the electronic medical record that matched each patient's specific insurance plan. Specifically, written comments revealed that both the NP and LLVN experienced hurdles with the processing of payment. The providers expressed a sense of responsibility to tackle the insurance and payment process on their own, attributing their challenges to their own personal learning curves. Open-ended comments related to examples of scenarios that represented wait time and crowd management scenarios indicated that the grouping of patient arrivals, especially around break times, and at the end of the day were most challenging to handle. One provider noted that it is problematic when the wait list builds up and feel that patients lack sympathy should a break be needed or when patients are turned away at the end of the shift so that the provider can complete remaining administrative duties. In terms of themes that emerged regarding the complexity of managing patients' clinical expectations at each clinic visit is the frequently encountered patient demand for antibiotic treatment. A few comments noted that providers face misconstrued

expectations about illness and present with requests for treatment before assessment has begun. In response, providers noted they do their best to educate about the patient's illness and what warrants antibiotic treatment, but do become overwhelmed by persistent, demanding patients.

Post In-Service Completion Survey

Thirty-four surveys were collected following the final A MENTOR in-service session in February 2014. Of the 33 surveys, 24 were completed by nurse practitioners and nine were completed by licensed vocational nurses. The average overall survey score out of a total of 5 possible was 4.55 for the whole group (n = 33). This score represented the general confidence level of both nurse practitioners and licensed vocational nurses in addressing patient concerns across all categories: billing, facility, clinical and empathy. For managing billing concerns alone, the average score among the thirty-three providers was 4.21, the lowest score across all categories. Confidence level around facility related concerns was 4.48 on average and 4.58 for confidence managing clinical related expectations. Comfort level with empathy and active listening was high at a mean of 4.88. The family nurse practitioners (n = 24) reported an average confidence level of 4.58 across all categories related to customer service. The licensed vocational nurses (n = 9) reported an average confidence level of 4.50 across all categories.

Addressing and managing patient expectations around billing and insurance issues scored lowest among all customer service related topics by both the NPs and the LVNs, 4.25 and 4.11, respectively. Confidence around managing facility issues was scored at a mean of 4.46 by the NPs and 4.56 by the LVNs. Confidence in managing patients' clinical expectations was rated as 4.63 by the NPs following the A MENTOR training

and 4.44 by the LVNs. Again, offering empathy and utilizing active listening as a customer service strategy during the clinical visit was scored highest by both the NPs and LVNs, 4.88 and 4.89, respectively. No differences were found between the NPs and the LVNs in the post-evaluation course survey.

When comparing average scores prior to and following the A MENTOR training sessions from the pre-evaluation and post-evaluation surveys, confidence and comfort level in managing patients' anticipated concerns about billing, wait times, and clinical plan expectations increased for both the NPs and LVNs. It is important to note that the change in group size between the LVNs attending the initial in-service and those attending the final in-service along with the post-educational survey did not allow for differences in scores to be measured.

Although more survey responses were collected after the final education session, few providers responded to the open ended questions. Only two respondents provided answers to the free response question regarding implementation of a change of practice into their routine. One nurse practitioner commented that her plan to manage waiting patients following the training involved addressing waiting patients, ensuring good eye contact, and apologizing for the wait. Another provider echoed the A MENTOR principles noting that improved customer service can be driven by early acknowledgement of the patient in the wait area.

DISCUSSION

High patient satisfaction in any healthcare setting has been shown to drive quality of care, patient loyalty, compliance with plan of care, trust, and even decrease the rate of liability (Kessler & Mylod, 2011). It is the responsibility of the healthcare organization or agency to promote positive patient outcomes and satisfaction. Since 2008, when hospitals began regularly reporting patient satisfaction to the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services through survey consulting services, an increase in satisfaction has been steadily observed (Convery, Mylod, & Spath, 2008). However, patient satisfaction reports alone may not provide enough specific information to identify issues that would spur a change in process (Blakemore, 2013).

In the ambulatory care setting and convenient care setting, the first point of the clinical encounter occurs between the health care provider and the patient. Thus, it makes sense then to dive deeper into the total patient experience during this provider-patient interaction, as research has shown that the clinician may be the most significant factor in determining the patient's satisfaction with their medical experience (Vukmir, 2006). This quality improvement project aimed to focus on this point of interaction in the convenient care setting that occurs between the patient and the care team that consists of both a nurse practitioner and licensed vocational nurse. Empowering healthcare providers in the area of customer service is not only beneficial to the building of patient loyalty, but critical to a shift towards patient-centered care within the ambulatory care setting. Murdock and Griffin (2013) state that "a patient-centered focus, communication, and a trusting relationship between patients and healthcare providers is what improves patient satisfaction. Patients whose time is respected and those who are kept informed are more

likely to have more patience, which, in turn, increases their satisfaction.” (p. 44, para. 4). Therefore, understanding what specific issues represent possible areas of concern raised by the patient in the convenient care setting is only the first step. Actively involving and engaging providers such as the nurse practitioner and licensed vocational nurse when it comes to the proactive handling of anticipated patient concerns becomes the next logical next step in the direction of patient-centered care. Thinking from a patient-centered standpoint and recognizing that customer service is an important aspect of addressing a patient in a holistic manner is not new to the nursing field (Williams, 1998). Nurse practitioners and licensed vocational nurses have been taught to think preventively and focus on all factors of the patient’s experience that impact their perception of their care and health. A MENTOR serves as the framework by which organizations concerned with preventing patient concerns can empower their providers in further building their customer service skill set.

Overall patient satisfaction in this particular convenient care setting region is known to be high. Not surprising then are the overall high baseline self-rated confidence scores reported on the provider surveys. Only the LVNs’ average scores fell below 4.0 in the area of billing and insurance at a mean of 3.75. This might be explained by the fact that the LVN role in this particular convenient care setting had been incorporated into the current care delivery structure just two months prior to the start of the A MENTOR training. All other scores at baseline were greater than 4.0 out of a possible 5.0. Yet, patient concerns continue to be called into the call center, presenting regular challenges for not only managers, but the providers who are informed of each filed concern through the handling process. A patient concern should be “regarded as a tool for education” and

health care organizations hold the responsibility of supporting the medical professionals they employ in preventing the occurrence of the incident “in the first place” (Norman, 2009, p. 11). Although no significant differences were found between the overall scores prior to and after A MENTOR, the goal of improvement and empowerment was met as evidenced by an increase in survey in nearly all areas of customer service. The fact that a measureable change in the positive direction was observed when the baseline was already high is indicative of the value of the A MENTOR training experience.

Improved scores are certainly a success of this quality improvement project. However, scores without actual change in practice may not be meaningful in the long term. The observed, though subtle, changes occurring at the clinic level may be a more powerful indicator of the impact of the A MENTOR training. Seeing nurse practitioners and licensed vocational nurses team up and revisit the use of the Ask Me 3® was an exciting observation. These actions demonstrate A MENTOR’s ability to drive behavioral change at the clinic level by reframing the message and discovering that the benefit of such a resource extends beyond its original intent of improving health literacy among patients to improving satisfaction which may, in turn, improve treatment plan adherence.

The insight gained from the pre survey in-service questionnaire was valuable to narrowing the curricula to areas and scenarios that challenged the providers most. Examples of challenges were generally consistent with managers’ experience handling patient concerns on a regular basis. This consistency was key information because it meant that the health professionals at the clinic level shared similar experiences with evidence viewed by the managers which demonstrates particular areas needing

improvement and support. Even more interesting were comments pertaining to insurance and billing processes where practitioners verbalized a need for clarification despite several attempts to use agency provided references. Self-reflection and self-determination were additional themes derived from those who expressed full ownership of the challenge, blaming it on their personal learning curves. While it is commendable to see characteristics of autonomy and self-determination among the nurse practitioners and licensed vocational nurses, the impression that learning the billing process, or any other aspect of care on their own is necessary is important to consider from a leadership viewpoint. A MENTOR's framework and education sessions provided guides for managing these issues and called upon team members to learn from each other, work together, and even practice through difficult patient cases together.

One of the benefits seen during the training was the group interaction and idea sharing that naturally ensued following a role play activity or through discussion of a case scenario. Not only did the attendees actively participate through each topic, they were able to provide strong solutions to common challenges via the A MENTOR construct. This was best highlighted during the third session that began with role play and discussion before talking points about preventing facility concerns was even presented. Through these exercises, they became one team, a think tank if you will, and empowered each other through the group dynamics at play. When the talking points were revealed, it was evident that their suggestions were not mere momentary thoughts, but the actual solutions framed by A MENTOR.

Role play opportunities during staff meetings or field rounds are requested most when area and agency leaders inquire how support can be best given to nurse practitioner

or licensed vocational nursing staff. Behavior change may then depend on behavior modeling which extends beyond a lesson plan or one time exposure to the A MENTOR framework. Investing time into the development of team members who then might motivate others through their actions should be a priority at the managerial level, as this influences the degree to which positive change not only occurs but is also perpetuated (Grol & Grimshaw, 2003).

The A MENTOR approach translates well to any healthcare setting because the patient's perceived experience determines their view of the level of quality of care rendered and ultimately builds loyalty to that system. The project as a whole is generalizable and applicable in the training of both clinically licensed professionals as well as support staff. The A MENTOR training was designed to be effective under time constraints and structured to tackle one focus area at a time while sequentially revisiting prior topics for reinforcement. Cost was not an issue as this training eased seamlessly into existing, budgeted staff meetings. A similar strategy can be utilized in implementing the A MENTOR framework and education format into other healthcare settings in order to remain cost-effective. It would be interesting to implement this plan in settings with patient satisfaction ratings below benchmark standards to truly appreciate the advantages of teaching team members to think from the patient's view and manage them proactively. Incorporating this framework as a foundation for customer service training of all new hires in the convenient care or ambulatory care setting may be a beneficial and proactive step in level setting all team members from the initial onboarding phase and carrying them through the hands-on portion of orientation. Therefore, the principles within A MENTOR can be used to guide patient interactions between patients and hospital service

management staff just as it can guide exchanges between patients and primary care outpatient medical assistants. A MENTOR is also useful at a systems level because the patient's medical experience does not only start and end with their diagnosis and treatment, rather, it begins from the moment they enter the general environment where care will ultimately be provided. Therefore, this framework applies to any aspect of the patient's care *process* which might begin with the information desk personnel and end with the radiology technician. If healthcare professionals and staff are able to think from the perspective of the patient, they will be empowered to anticipate their needs, acknowledge their concerns, recognize when more clarification is needed, and impart clear expectations for the remainder of their health journey. The system as a whole can then exceed patients' expectations through actions that establish rapport and build mutual partnerships at every encounter. This quality improvement project represents the early implementation of Scotti et al.'s (2007) vision of a high-performance work system within the healthcare arena where organizational processes impact levels of service quality, and consequently, patient satisfaction. A MENTOR provides the framework for healthcare practitioners who are called to action "to enjoy working on making patients' care more effective, efficient, safe, and friendly" (Grol & Grimshaw, 2010, p. 1229). Ultimately, striving for a culture of service in healthcare leads to high quality, patient-centered care that transforms the patient-provider relationship, spurs organizational loyalty, and optimizes patient outcomes (Huppertz, Smith, & Bombard, 2014).

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APPENDIX A

A MENTOR SAMPLE EDUCATION SLIDES AND TALKING POINTS

Patient Concerns – What does the Literature Say?

Principles:

- Patient-provider relationship *transforms into a partnership* in all aspects
- “Everyone is a Customer” (Reisberg, 1996)
 - Security and sense of control
 - Recognition
 - Fairness in treatment
 - Gain trust early
- Patient Satisfaction, Perception, and Quality of Care
 - Perception of care & Satisfaction are linked
 - Customer Concerns provide insight into the patient’s perception of clinical experience
 - Expectations, Past experiences, Attitudes (Alrubaiee & Alkaa’ida, 2011)

Patient Concerns – What does the Literature Say?

- Increased Satisfaction:
 - Decreases liability
 - Increases loyalty
 - Increases adherence to plan of care and follow up
- “The Gift of Customer Complaints” (Stickler & Schumacher, 2003)
 - Complaints are not failures, rather, complaints are opportunities for corrective, preventative action
- **Take Away: *Patient Concerns are Preventable***

Patient Concerns – Be “A MENTOR”

Be “A MENTOR”

- **A**nticipate and address expectations
- **M**anage the patient as a customer
- **E**stablish rapport
- **N**egotiate and partner
- **T**reat the clinical and customer diagnoses
- **O**ffer clarification as needed
- **R**ecognize concerns and reinforce realistic solutions/expectations

Boutary, 2012

A MENTOR – Addressing Billing Topics

- **Anticipate and address expectations**
 - Provider: “Hello Mrs. Smith. Welcome to our clinic. My name is [Insert Name] and I am a [Insert Role]. Have you been to our clinic before?”
 - Patient: “No.”
 - Provider: “Well, I am happy to meet you today. Let’s begin by getting you checked into our system. Do you have an insurance plan you would like to use today?”
 - Patient: “Yes.”
 - Provider: “In our setting, most of our visits are [Insert Cost]. Lab tests needed do add additional cost. I see here that we are in-network with your insurance plan and that you have an office visit copay. For this visit, you will owe the copay at the end just like at your doctor’s office, and the remainder which is the difference between the total and the copay will be billed to your insurance. What I am unable to determine are the exact details of your plan. So you may receive a bill depending on how much your insurance covers after your copay amount.”

Customer Concerns – A MENTOR – Billing

- **Manage the patient as a customer**
 - Provider: “Do you have any further questions around charges or billing that I can answer before we begin?”
 - Patient: “So you will just send me a bill if I owe anything more?”
 - Provider: “Yes, we will bill you for any amount due after the insurance claim is processed. It is important to me that patients understand our billing procedure, so thank you for allowing me to explain this before we begin.”
- **Establish rapport**
 - Patient: “I just feel so stressed and sick and put off getting seen because I’m working full time and have 3 kids at home.”
 - Provider: “I am hearing you Mrs. Smith. You do so much for others, balancing your family and career. I am glad you came in to take care of you. This is your time.”

A MENTOR – Addressing Billing Topics

- **Negotiate and partner**
 - Provider: “Your insurance is out of network with us.”
 - Patient: “But I have really good insurance and never pay more than \$25.”
 - Provider: “I see here that your particular plan is an HMO and that [identify medical group] is listed on your card. That means that your insurance has determined that [medical group] is the medical setting where health services are billable to your insurance plan. Because we are not [designated medical group], we are unable to bill this insurance plan. However, we are more than happy to see you today as a patient should you choose to pay out of pocket. You may also try to reimburse on your own, however, we are unable to guarantee that your plan will reimburse services here today.”

A MENTOR – Addressing Billing Topics

- **Treat the clinical and customer diagnoses**
 - Spend time explaining what the diagnoses are and your plan of care.
 - Address the customer-service related diagnoses:
 - “So pleased you chose our clinic today. Since we take your insurance, know that you can return for other services.”
 - “Remember that if you have any questions regarding services covered, please call your insurance company for details.”
- **Offer clarification as needed**
 - “Do you have any further questions I can answer before we end today?”
- **Recognize concerns and reinforce realistic solutions/expectations**
 - Reinforce the billing aspect when you print the receipt.
 - Explain the breakdown of charges and the amount billed to insurance.
 - “You can also call our Billing department through our patient call center as needed and here is the number: [insert number].”

“A MENTOR” – Practice Scenarios

- Billing Related:
 - Patient came to the clinic for a “sore throat” and was prepared to pay the advertised amount out of pocket for the visit. The patient was shocked when the charges were over what was expected. Patient called her concern into the call center.
- Clinical Related:
 - Patient states that the practitioner diagnosed her with a “cold” and after 2 days, she is still sick. Patient had hoped that she would receive antibiotics for her cold but did not. She is disappointed that she is not better and asking for a “z-pak” to get rid of her symptoms.
- Facility Related:
 - Patient arrived to the clinic close to the lunch break and was the third on the sign in list. The next two patients were seen and when it was her turn, the patient was told she could not be seen as the clinic would be closing for a mandatory lunch break. The patient was upset because she arrived before the lunch break and expected to be seen.

“A MENTOR” – Tools

- **#1 Tool is YOU**
 - Take the time to explain the process to the patient and ensure clear understanding.
- Patient Education Brochures
- Organizational level existing resources
- Clinic Partner for Support

APPENDIX B**ASK ME 3[®]**

APPENDIX C

PRE A MENTOR TRAINING SURVEY

Please answer the following questions below. All responses are confidential and anonymous. Thank you for your participation.

1. Clinic Role (please circle): NP or LVN

2. How confident are you with the billing process in the clinic? (please circle)

5	4	3	2	1
Very	Somewhat	Neither	Somewhat	Very
Confident	Confident	Confident nor	Unconfident	Unconfident
		Unconfident		

3. Please describe a situation around billing/insurance that was most challenging for you.

4. How confident are you with managing patients' expectations around clinic wait times, crowd management, and hours of operation? (please circle)

5	4	3	2	1
Very	Somewhat	Neither	Somewhat	Very
Confident	Confident	Confident nor	Unconfident	Unconfident
		Unconfident		

5. Please describe a situation around wait times, crowd management, and hours of operation that was most challenging for you.

6. How confident are you with managing the patient's clinical/treatment expectations? (please circle)

5	4	3	2	1
Very	Somewhat	Neither	Somewhat	Very
Confident	Confident	Confident nor	Unconfident	Unconfident
		Unconfident		

7. Please describe a situation around a patient's clinical/treatment expectations that was most challenging for you.

8. I am comfortable offering empathy and actively listening to patients' concerns during every clinical visit. (please circle)

5	4	3	2	1
Very	Somewhat	Neither	Somewhat	Very
Comfortable	Comfortable	Comfortable	Uncomfortable	Uncomfortable
		nor		
		Uncomfortable		

9. Please describe a situation around empathizing with or actively listening to patient concerns that was challenging for you.

APPENDIX D

POST A MENTOR TRAINING SURVEY

Please answer the following questions below. All responses are confidential and anonymous. Thank you for your participation.

1. Clinic Role (please circle): NP or LVN

2. How confident are you with the billing process in the clinic following the A MENTOR presentations? (please circle)

5	4	3	2	1
Very Confident	Somewhat Confident	Neither Confident nor Unconfident	Somewhat Unconfident	Very Unconfident

3. How confident are you with managing patients' expectations around clinic wait times, crowd management, and hours of operation following the A MENTOR presentations? (please circle)

5	4	3	2	1
Very Confident	Somewhat Confident	Neither Confident nor Unconfident	Somewhat Unconfident	Very Unconfident

4. How confident are you with managing the patient's clinical/treatment expectations following the A MENTOR presentations? (please circle)

5	4	3	2	1
Very Confident	Somewhat Confident	Neither Confident nor Unconfident	Somewhat Unconfident	Very Unconfident

5. How comfortable are you offering empathy and actively listening to patients' concerns during every clinical visit following the A MENTOR presentations? (please circle)

5	4	3	2	1
Very Comfortable	Somewhat Comfortable	Neither Comfortable	Somewhat Uncomfortable	Very Uncomfortable
			nor Uncomfortable	

6. Is there anything you have changed or plan to change in your practice since the A MENTOR framework was initially presented?

7. If so, how have you or how are you going to implement this into your practice?

APPENDIX E

TABLES OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL

Table 1

Patient Satisfaction and Quality of Care in the Retail Health Care Setting

Author/Year (citation)	Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Authors Conclusions/Limitations
Hunter et al. (2009)	Analysis of patient satisfaction with care at RCs provided by FNPs and PAs.	Design: Descriptive, prospective design. Key Variables: Patient satisfaction survey responses.	Sample: N = 684 pts (May 2006 – June 2007). Setting: MediMin clinics in Phoenix & Scottsdale, Arizona.	Self-report sample survey, ie. Patient satisfaction survey: 8 multiple choice questions and 1 open-ended question. Demographics data also reported.	Descriptive Statistics: Satisfaction – Very satisfied or satisfied (95%). Would return (98% reported yes).	Conclusions: Homogeneity of answers indicated RCs providing satisfactory services to clients. FNP demand increased due to RC desirability. Limitations: One geographical area and one RC organization.
Mehrota et al. (2009)	Compare care at RCs for 3 acute conditions versus other settings.	Retrospective convenience sample of claims data. Key variable: Quality of care.	Claims data from 2005 – 2006 in Minnesota RCs. N = 2100 episodes in RCs.	Episodes of Care Matching: RC episode matched on 5 variables to episodes in other settings. Matched cases = 3 acute visits and demographics.	No difference between follow-up visits in RCs and other settings. Episodes initiating in EDs vs. RCs = more f/u visits (16.0% vs. 24.5%)*.	Conclusions: QOC in RCs comparable; NPs QOC similar to physicians. Limitations: Limited to 3 acute diagnoses, may not generalize to other conditions.

Author/Year (citation)	Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Authors Conclusions/Limitations
				Quality of Care (QOC) Measurement: RAND Corporation's Quality Assurance Tools. Rates of preventive services within 3 months after first visit.	QOC: No difference in QOC (RCs vs. PCP and UCs). QOC lower in EDs than RCs*. Preventive care received less in ED vs. RC*.	
Woodburn et al. (2007)	Assess the QOC of acute pharyngitis management in the RC setting based on national clinical guidelines.	Retrospective analysis of convenience. Key Variables: Rate of adherence to national guidelines for acute pharyngitis management.	Sample: Convenience Sample. N = 55, 331 patient visits for acute pharyngitis. Setting: 28 RCs in Minnesota and Maryland.	Antibiotic treatment rate for RST (+). Antibiotic treatment rate for RST (-). Rate of confirmatory GABHS culture negative RST.	RST (+) = 99.75% given antibiotics. RST (-) = 99.05% not given antibiotics. RST (-) = 99.2% Confirmatory GABHS sent.	Provider training supports high rates of adherence to national guidelines for acute pharyngitis. Appropriate management = decreased overuse of antibiotics. National guideline adherence demonstrates clinical quality.

Note. FNPs = family nurse practitioners; PAs = physician assistants; yrs = years; wrt = with respect to; RCs = retail clinics; QOC = quality of care; EDs = emergency departments; PCP = primary care physician; UC = urgent care; NP = nurse practitioner; f/u = follow up; RST = rapid strep test; GABHS = group A beta-hemolytic strep; pts = patients; EMR = electronic medical record.

* $p < .05$.

Table 2

Patient Perception and Provider Relationships

Author/Year (citation)	Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Authors Conclusions/Limitations
Alrubaiee & Alkaa'ida (2011)	Investigate the relationship between patient perceptions of care, trust and its impact on patient satisfaction.	Design: Descriptive, quantitative study Key Variables: Healthcare quality, patient satisfaction, and patient trust.	Sample: N = 290 surveys. Setting: Four hospitals in Amman, Jordan.	Questionnaires based on SERVQUAL scale (adapted).	Patient perception of quality of care directly impacts satisfaction. Satisfaction impacts patient trust.	Conclusions: "Healthcare service quality ... a vital determinant of patient satisfaction and patient trust" (p.114). Patient perception of the provider influences confidence in care and services rendered.
Epstein et al. (2005)	Present principles and creation of methods for assessing PCC. Patient-physician interactions.	Literature review and analysis design. Comprehensive review.	n/a	Review of literature of validated related survey measuring tools.	Interpreting patient ratings of their clinician should be done carefully. Measures do not account for patient contextual factors (i.e., personality; acuity of illness)	PCC plays into high-quality care. PCCs and patient-centeredness are separate yet similar constructs. Survey measures "provide a global impression of the relationship" (p. 1524).

Note. PCC = Patient-centered communication.

Table 3

Complaints Handling and Service Training

Author/Year (citation)	Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Authors Conclusions/Limitations
Hsieh (2012)	Understand the nature of complaints and how they are handled by hospital staff.	Design: Case study. Key Variables: Complaints categories.	Sample: N = 665 complaints from 1998 – 2000. Setting: Taiwanese teaching hospital.	Face-to-face interviews. Semi-structured questionnaire. Hospital complaints system database.	Thematic analysis (% of complaints received by category): Humaneness = 49.9% of complaints. Care/treatment = 17.9% of complaints. Access/availability = 10.5% of complaints.	Conclusions: Understanding complaint trends influences interventions towards service quality improvement.
Mayer et al. (1998)	Investigate the effect of customer service training on patient satisfaction.	Design: Pre-/post-test, non-experimental. Intervention: 8-hour customer service training (ED staff). Key Variables: Pt. satisfaction scores; complaints/compliments data.	Sample: Control group (patients presenting May 1994 – April 1995). Study group (all patients presenting May 1995 – April 1996). Setting: ED; Virginia.	Measures: Satisfaction surveys. Complaints and compliments data. Acuity. Turnaround times. Volume.	Compliments increased >100% (control vs. study)*. Complaints dropped to rate of 0.6 per 1,000 visits*. Patient satisfaction increased (control vs. study).**	Formal customer service training for clinical staff results in increased patient compliments and satisfaction scores. A decrease is seen in complaints.

Note. ED = emergency department; Pt. = patient.

* $p < .00001$; ** $p < .001$.

